

Conservation agriculture across soil and environmental aridity levels

Conservation Agriculture (CA) is a farming system that combines efficiency and low cost to prevent soil degradation, and promote soil protection through reduced or no tillage, soil cover, and crop rotations. Compared to ploughed soil, CA improves soil organic carbon accumulation in the topsoil, soil health and biodiversity, bearing capacity, widening the window for field operations reduces erosion, labour per unit area, and production costs, and increases yield stability¹, and usually also farmer profit. CA increases water availability for crops through a reduce water evaporation, which improve yield at increasing aridity. In arid condition, fuel consumption for tillage accounts for 40-60% of the total cost. Thus, CA dramatically reduce the cultivation cost compared to the conventional, and may increase profit even when yields are slightly lower than conventional.

Avoiding tillage, the main driver of soil degradation, is CA cornerstone. Using a direct drill is necessary, but not sufficient. Efficient CA systems require a systemic redesigning of the management: (i) suitable machinery for sod, residue-covered soils, (ii) effective and timely weed, pathogen and pest control, (iii) adjust fertilisation strategies, (iv) adapted crop genotypes, augmented seed rate, and slightly earlier sowing date and (v) diversified rotations.

Figure 1 A direct seed drill sowing corn under NT on the residues of a cover crop, northern Italy (left), and a particular of the sowing rows before its closing (right). Picture owner: S. Saia

KEYWORDS

no tillage; cover crop; rotation; drought; weed; pest; diseases, water balance

AUTHORSHIP

Sergio Saia^{a,b}, Milos di Gregorio^a, Francesco G. S. Angeletti^a, Fatma Ezzahra Ben Azaiez^a, Fabio Castronovo^a, Manel Ibrahim^{a,c}, Farah Mlaiki^{a,d}; Marco Mariotti^a.

a) Dept. Veterinary Science, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy; **b)** Centre for Climate Change Impact (CIRSEC), University of Pisa, Italy; **c)** Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie, Université de Carthage, Tunisia ; **d)** Department of Geology, Faculty of Sciences of Tunis, University of Tunis El Manar, Tunis, Tunisia.

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